

INITIAL DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

PERSONALITY IN COMMUNITY ECOLOGY RESPONSES: INTEGRATING THE BEHAVIOUR AND SPECIES INTERACTIONS OF A MARINE INVADER — PINCER

APRIL 2020

DMP PHILOSOPHY

PinCER defines “data” in the context of the MSCA-IF, Contract as “all digital outputs that are direct products of the research action”. As such, we aim for a Digital Output Management Plan that applies FAIR Principles outlined below to all PinCER digital outputs.

The PinCER digital outputs will all be centralized in DOI-issued digital storage repositories (Open Science Framework project, 'OSF', osf.io/rnz7q/), to provide long-term, searchable, and accessible data storage.

The initial project DMP will be updated at PinCER 12-month and 24-month milestones (Jan 12 2021, Jan 12 2022), to implement this philosophy to outputs beyond just experimental and field data.

DATA SUMMARY

- *State the purpose of the data collection/generation*
- *Explain the relation to the objectives of the project*
- *Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected*
- *Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)*
- *Specify the origin of the data*
- *State the expected size of the data (if known)*
- *Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful*

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Data will be generated in two experimental work packages (WP1, WP2 in the project proposal, hereafter '*experimental data*'), and in the meta-analysis work package (WP3, hereafter '*meta-analysis data*').

These three work packages are each designed as independent empirical studies to test specific research hypotheses; therefore, the primary use and purpose of data collection will be for input into data analysis for hypothesis testing.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Experimental data to be collected, their form and format are as follow:

1. Data collection from fieldwork/sampling will include water quality parameters, GPS locations of sampling sites, weight and length data for fish etc. collected by directly by researchers (specific measurement equipment is to be determined based on availability). The format of data from fieldwork will be originally be recorded by hand in datasheets in teams of two (one person measuring, one recording). This physical data, which will then will then be entered in excel (.xlsx) spreadsheets.
2. Physical samples will be collected of animal tissue and of animal gut contents. Physical tissue and gut content samples will be held frozen in the laboratory for use of stable isotope analysis of tissue and quantitative gut content analysis. As the planned analysis for these samples will consume the samples, these are not in a form that require long-term storage after use.
3. A physical journal for animal experiments will be maintained in accordance with Danish animal ethics regulations (Bekendtgørelse om dyreforsøg, Kapitel 4). This will contemporaneously record the details of animal experiments at each step, e.g. collection and transport of animals, when and which experiments are used on animals, etc.
4. All other data will be collected digitally in the laboratory, including video analysis of behaviour, behavioural variables from video processing, stable isotope abundances, and quantitative gut content analysis. The format of experimental data collected digitally within the laboratory will be collected and stored in the following formats:

Experimental Digital Data	Collection Method	Format
Video data of behavioural experiments	Recording using Logitech Brio, and Logitech Capture software	stored as .mp4
Video processing data	Collected via non-proprietary software (e.g. ToxTrac, doi: 10.1111/2041-210X.12874)	output to .csv
Stable isotope data	Analysed externally (e.g. Monash Water Studies Centre (WS-ASIF), wsc-asif.blogspot.com)	excel and .csv files
Gut content data	Obtained by quantitative analysis of gut content samples	excel and .csv files
Data analysis code and outputs	Data will be processed and analyzed using the open access R Statistical Program	.csv files (data output) .R files (code) .Rdata files (statistical models)

Meta-analysis data will be entirely digital, as extracted from online databases (e.g. Web of Science, Scopus), extracted data from published papers or publish datasets from supplementary information and public repositories (e.g. datadryad.org, osf.io), and received from direct correspondence with third parties. The main types and format of meta-analysis data are as follows:

Meta-Analytic Digital Data	Format
Bibliographic data extracted from online scientific databases	Cross compatible bibliographic formations (e.g. .bib, .bibx), with associated published papers stored as PDFs
Systematic review screening and processing databases (e.g. to record my inclusion and exclusion reasons in the title/abstract screening process)	excel and .csv files
Data extracted by myself from reading and compiling data from published papers and public repositories	excel and .csv files
Third party datasets obtained from public repositories or received through correspondence	excel and .csv files data will also be stored in the original format that the data was received in
Data analysis code and outputs via the open access R Statistical Program	.csv files (data output) .R files (code) .Rdata files (statistical models)

Output formats are all non-proprietary and compatible with open access data analysis software. All data collection described above will be quantitative, although qualitative data may also be collected at all stages as notes annotating physical datasheets and digital data files.

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Experimental data will be original. Re-use of existing datasets for experimental data is not currently planned.

Meta-analysis data inputs will be entirely from reuse of published and unpublished third party datasets, but the data outputs from processing and modelling of this collected can be considered an original product of this project.

What is the origin of the data?

Experimental data will be obtained by independent sampling and laboratory experiments conducted by myself. Stable isotope data will be obtained via a third party, as this must be processed at an external stable isotope analysis laboratory (e.g. the Water Studies Centre, Monash University, Australia).

Meta-analysis data will be obtained by conducting a systematic review of published literature, extracted from scientific databases. Additional data will be obtained from contacting authors, where their published data is insufficiently complete to be included in our analyses.

What is the expected size of the data?

Experimental data will be approximately 500GB across the two experimental work packages. This will primarily be due to the 100-200 video files per experiment of up to 1GB each.

Meta-analysis data will be approximately 3-5 GB total. The largest components of this are expected to be PDF copies of published papers, and the output .Rdata models from data analysis.

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

The two primary groups that may be able to re-use data from this project are: 1) research and academic audiences with an interest in behavioural ecology, invasive species ecology, or the round goby as a specific study species; and 2) Decision makers in environmental management and policy. Relevant decision making bodies include those with a focus on the Baltic Sea ecosystems, such as the Working Group on Introductions and Transfers of Marine Organisms for the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea 'ICES', and the Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission - Helsinki Commission (HELCOM).

FAIR DATA

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

- *Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision).*
- *Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?*
- *Outline naming conventions used.*
- *Outline the approach towards search keyword.*
- *Outline the approach for clear versioning.*
- *Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how.*

Upon publication, all data that contributes to the analysis and conclusions of a publication will primarily be made publically available via Open Science Framework (OSF) (osf.io/ztdcx) and GitHub/Zenodo (zenodo.org/communities/pincer/).

It is expected that 3 - 4 separate OSF project repositories will be established, one for each planned publication. OSF projects allocate DOIs to each project, include a 'Tags' section for searchable keywords and a 'Wiki' section for a detailed description of the project's purpose and contents. Therefore, all datasets that form part of these projects will be readily discoverable. Quantitative datasets will be uploaded with metadata files. This will include descriptors for all variables used, based on standard terminological conventions used in behavioural ecology and food-web ecology, as well as any contextual data that is essential understanding the dataset, such as the time and date of experiments used, ID of observers etc.

Data analysis will be conducted within the R Statistical Program using GitHub as version control. Github allows integration with OSF projects, such that all scripts /code for analysis as well as input and output data from analysis will be publically available through OSF. All analysis code will be annotated with the intention of making it understandable by academic peers. Upon publication of output datasets, data held in GitHub will also be archived on the Zenodo PinCER Collection to preserve a long-term time-stamped version-controlled copy of the digital analysis output and datasets associated with the publication

Through both OSF and Zenodo, all outputs will then be broadly findable and usable by target audiences using a standard open license for use (e.g. License: CC-By Attribution 4.0 International)
Additional paid repositories may only be used if required by publishers.

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

- *Specify which data will be made openly available. If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so.*
- *Specify how the data will be made available.*
- *Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?*
- *Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited.*
- *Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions.*

Data related to publications and the analysis and conclusions therein will be publically available following publication, via a public OSF and Github/Zenodo repositories. I do not intend to collect and upload data in proprietary software formats, so all data will be widely accessible.

Data from one project may be kept private for a limited period of time (by setting the OSF project Repository to private) in the case that it will form a significant contribution to a future planned project/publication and publishing it would jeopardize the publication of that future project.

Some project data will not be uploaded to these open OSF project repositories where is it not practical, specifically hard copies of data sheets, original video files of behavioural experiments, although these will be maintained for a minimum period (5 years from project completion or publication of research, whichever is later) and may be accessed on reasonable request.

2.3 Making data interoperable:

- *Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.*
- *Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability. If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?*

Quantitative datasets will be uploaded to OSF and Github/Zenodo with metadata files. This will include descriptors for all variables used, based on standard terminological conventions used in behavioural ecology and food-web ecology, as well as any contextual data that is essential understanding the dataset, such as the time and date of experiments used, ID of observers etc. I expect that all variables and contextual information will be able to be described in plain English, so that all data will be semantically interoperable.

It is expected that all data will also have broad technical interoperability, as it will be recorded in widely used file formats compatible with open access software. This includes: widely cross compatible .csv files for quantitative databases; .bib bibliographic files usable with open access bibliographic software Zotero; and .R and .Rdata files for use with the open access R Statistical Program).

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- *Specify how the data will be licensed to permit the widest reuse possible.*
- *Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed.*

- *Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.*
- *Describe data quality assurance processes.*
- *Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable.*

Data will be re-usable using standard licensing under the OSF framework. I intend to use licensing requiring acknowledgement and citation of the original source (e.g. License: CC-By Attribution 4.0 International). Data will remain on OSF and Zenodo repositories indefinitely.

It is expected that data will be made available at the point of publication, although data will also be available earlier in cases where a manuscript is submitted to a preprint server prior to publication (e.g. bioRxiv.org, EcoEvoRxiv.org).

Data from a project may be kept private for a limited period of time (by setting an OSF project Repository to private), only where it forms a significant contribution to another planned project/publication and publishing it would jeopardize the publication of that future project.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

- *Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs*
- *Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project*
- *Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation*

As the primary researcher, I (Nicholas Moran) am responsible for data management, curation and preservation of data during the life of the project (2 year). Following completion of the project I will remain responsible for long-term preservation of all published data stored in repositories (OSF, GitHub/Zenodo), and keep a copy of all project data personal cloud storage (www.dropbox.com). The supervisors (Prof. Andre Visser and Dr Jane Behrens) will be responsible for long-term preservation of the DTU departmental copy of all digital data on DTU servers, as well as all remaining physical data at DTU Aqua, Lyngby.

There is no cost for data preservation on publically available servers, while maintenance of personal cloud storage is covered by the researcher (\$11.99AUD/ month). The time costs to the researcher of have been taken into account when planning the person-hours allocated to the project work packages.

There are no additional costs to DTU for the long-term preservation of the digital data on departmental servers and physical data in storage at DTU. Data will be stored for a minimum of 5 years following project completion or the final publication originating from this project (whichever is longer).

DATA SECURITY

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.

To ensure data is recoverable, copies of all digital data will be held on DTU departmental servers and on the researcher's personal cloud (Dropbox). Departmental servers will only be accessible to relevant DTU staff

(which will only include myself, and after the end of the project the supervisors, Prof. Andre Visser and Dr Jane Behrens). Data on the personal Dropbox is only accessible to the Nicholas Moran.

ETHICAL ASPECTS

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former.

This project involves the use of live animals, and relevant approvals for the experimentation on animals have been obtained (see PinCER project Deliverable D1.1). A physical journal for animal experiments will be maintained in accordance with Danish animal ethics regulations (Bekendtgørelse om dyreforsøg, Kapitel 4). This will contemporaneously record the details of animal experiments at each step, e.g. collection and transport of animals, when and which experiments are used on animals, etc. This journal will be stored along with all physical experimental data from this project, and maintained of a minimum of five years from the completion of animal experiments as required by regulations).

Data will not contain any personal or confidential information. Although, meta-analysis data will include records of correspondence with academics regarding their publications and the data therein. Although we do not consider this correspondence strictly confidential, we will treat this correspondence as private and sensitive in nature. Therefore, this data will be stored securely with other digital data, but redacted from datasets uploaded to public repositories. In addition, any primary datasets received from academics via correspondence will be redacted from published datasets.

OTHER

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using.

This data management plan follows and has been drafted in line with:

1. Research Data Procedure and Guidelines - DTU Aqua
2. DTU Policy of the Retention of Primary Material and Data
3. DTU Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
4. DTU Information Security Policy
5. Guidelines to rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications & Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020
6. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020

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